

EXPLICIT DAMAGE MODELLING OF COMPOSITES UNDER COMPRESSIVE LOADING

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ABSTRACT

In general, composite laminate failure in compression is more complicated than tensile failure because of additional failure modes such as sub-laminate buckling, local micro-buckling and kink band formation. Accurately modelling these failure modes in a continuum-based model presents considerable challenges. This work presents a high-fidelity integrated discrete-smearred crack approach for modelling notched composite laminates under compressive loads. The predicted failure loads and patterns compare well with experimental data and observations in the literature.

1 INTRODUCTION

In a previous work, Su *et al.* [1] modelled the progressive failure of open-hole composite laminates and captured major failure mechanisms of sublaminar-level scaled laminates and ply-level scaled laminates under compression [2]. However, smearred crack models may encounter mesh dependence and convergence problems. Another disadvantage is that a mesh design aligned with the fiber direction was necessary to model fiber splitting in the 0° plies [1]. Due to the smearing out of sharp cracks, interaction between matrix cracking and delamination could not be explicitly modelled. Recently, the floating node method was proposed to overcome these shortcomings and the tensile failure of open-hole laminates was accurately modelled [3]. Zhi *et al.* [4, 5] further developed a non-linear large deformation version of this method, applicable to laminates under more general loading conditions (*e.g.*, compression, impact). In this work, open-hole composite laminates subjected to compressive loading are analyzed using an integrated approach in which matrix cracking is explicitly and discretely modelled with the floating node method, fiber damage with smearred crack model and delamination with cohesive zone model. The results are compared with experimental data and observation from literature [2].

2 DAMAGE MODELS

In this section, the integrated numerical techniques for modelling intra-laminar and inter-laminar damage are briefly introduced.

2.1 Fiber-dominated damage model

Fiber-dominated damage under compression is mainly attributed to fiber microbuckling or kink-band formation. The physics behind this localized deformation behaviour is typically explained by fiber rotations due to initial fiber misalignment and subsequent matrix plastic deformation. An accurate modelling of kink-band formation includes the prediction of the width of kink band and its propagation angle. However, it remains difficult to model kink band formation at the ply level since micro-scale information cannot be easily incorporated into the classical continuum framework. Moreover, kink bands are sensitive to the initial defects and lateral support conditions. Therefore, a smearred crack model is adopted herein with combining a maximum stress criterion (X_c compressive strength)

$$\frac{\sigma_1}{X_c} = -1, \sigma_1 < 0 \quad (1)$$

and a linear damage evolution law (where G_{fc} is the so-called compressive intra-laminar fracture toughness)

$$d_f = \frac{\varepsilon_{1,f}(\varepsilon_1 - \varepsilon_{1,0})}{\varepsilon_1(\varepsilon_{1,f} - \varepsilon_{1,0})}, \quad (2)$$

$$\varepsilon_{1,f} = \frac{2G_f c}{X_c l_e}, \quad (3)$$

where $\varepsilon_{1,0}$ and $\varepsilon_{1,f}$ are the longitudinal strains at the initial damage and final damage, respectively. l_e is the characteristic length of the element.

2.2 Matrix-dominated damage model

Matrix cracks initiate in non-zero-degree plies at early stages of loading. In compression, the crack angle is usually non-zero ($\theta \neq 0$ in Fig. 1), unlike in tension [3-5]. A Mohr-Coulomb type failure theory is used for matrix compression failure [6]. Since matrix cracks usually propagate along the fiber direction, the fracture surface is aligned with the 1 direction. The tractions on the surface are given by

$$\begin{cases} \sigma_n = \frac{\sigma_2 + \sigma_3}{2} + \frac{\sigma_2 - \sigma_3}{2} \cos 2\theta + \tau_{23} \sin 2\theta \\ \tau_T = -\frac{\sigma_2 - \sigma_3}{2} \sin 2\theta + \tau_{23} \cos 2\theta \\ \tau_L = \tau_{12} \cos \theta + \tau_{31} \sin \theta \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Figure 1: Fracture plane of a matrix crack in a composite ply.

The onset criterion is given by

$$\begin{cases} \left(\frac{\tau_T}{S_T - \mu_T \sigma_n} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_L}{S_L - \mu_L \sigma_n} \right)^2 = 1 & \sigma_n < 0 \\ \left(\frac{\sigma_n}{Y_t} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_T}{S_T} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_L}{S_L} \right)^2 = 1 & \sigma_n \geq 0 \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where Y_t , S_T and S_L are transverse tensile strength, transverse shear strength and longitudinal shear strength, respectively. μ_T and μ_L are friction-like parameters, which are given as

$$\mu_T = -\frac{1}{\tan 2\theta_0}, \quad (6)$$

$$\mu_L = S_L \frac{\mu_T}{S_T}. \quad (7)$$

θ_0 is the fracture angle of matrix cracking under pure compression, which is approximately 53° from experimental observation of thermoset composites [6]. In a general stress state, the fracture angle θ is determined by searching the maximum failure index in Eq. (5) within the range of $-90^\circ \leq \theta < 90^\circ$ (interval: 5°).

Figure 2: Fracture plane of composites due to matrix cracking.

After crack initiation, cohesive elements are inserted to model the matrix crack with the floating node method, whereby the original element is partitioned into several sub-elements [3-5]. However, if unmodified, it is complicated to model an inclined crack ('configuration-1' in Fig. 2) using this method. Therefore, a vertical cohesive element but with an inclined coordinate system determined by the angle θ is used, following an efficient but approximate approach [7]. The failure caused by matrix cracking can then be modelled by the shear damage of the cohesive element. A test problem of pure transverse compressive failure of a laminate is given in Fig. 3, where the fracture angle is determined to be 55° . It should be noted that 53° fracture angle can be predicted if the searching interval becomes finer or advanced searching algorithm (*e.g.*, Golden section search) is employed.

Figure 3: Failure of $[90_4]$ composite laminate subjected to in-plane compressive loading.

2.3 Delamination model

Delamination is also modelled with a cohesive zone model but initiation is determined by

$$\left(\frac{\langle t_n \rangle}{t_n^0}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{t_s}{t_s^0}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{t_t}{t_t^0}\right)^2 = 1 \quad (8)$$

where t_n^0 , t_s^0 and t_t^0 are normal and shear interface strengths. Thereafter, a softening law similar to Eq. (2) is applied and the mixed-mode propagation follows power law criterion [5]. Normal compressive tractions do not contribute to delamination damage.

3 OPEN-HOLE COMPRESSION MODELLING

FE models of open-hole laminates are described and numerical results are given.

3.1 Numerical model

Lee and Soutis [2] have investigated the compressive failure mechanisms of laminates and also the size effects through experimental tests on unnotched and notched specimens with various stacking sequences. In this work, a numerical study was conducted to model the damage growth in laminates ($32 \text{ mm} \times 32 \text{ mm}$, hole diameter – 6.35 mm) with two typical lay-ups, ply-level scaled (PL) -- $[45_4/90_4/-$

$45_4/0_4]_s$ and sublaminates-level scaled (SL) -- $[45/90/-45/0]_{4s}$. The finite element models are shown in Fig. 4, where the discontinuous solid-shell element developed in [5] was used to discretize composite plies while the enriched cohesive element modelled the interfaces. A radial mesh of 0.5 mm element size was adopted for the region near the hole. Considering the symmetry of the problem, only a half FE model with symmetry boundary condition was created for the sake of efficiency. To study the mesh dependence of the proposed method, another two meshes shown in Fig. 5 were used for the modelling of the PL laminate. In ‘mesh-2’, an approximately aligned mesh around the hole was employed and the element size is 0.5mm. Similar mesh pattern was used in ‘mesh-3’ but with a refined mesh (0.25 mm). The total number of nodes used in ‘mesh-1’, ‘mesh-2’ and ‘mesh-3’ for the PL laminate is 112106, 120168 and 287568. Material properties used in the simulations are listed in Table 1. A thickness-scaled value is used for the compressive intra-laminar fracture toughness [8].

Ply properties		Ply properties		Interface properties	
E_{11} (GPa)	161	X_c (MPa)	1690	K (N/mm ³)	10^6
$E_{22}=E_{22}$ (GPa)	11.4	Y_t (MPa)	60	t_n^0 (MPa)	40
$G_{12}=G_{13}$ (GPa)	5.17	$S_T=S_L$ (MPa)	90	$t_s^0 = t_t^0$ (MPa)	50
G_{23} (GPa)	3.98	G_{fc} (kJ/m ²)	25.9	G_{IC} (kJ/m ²)	0.2
$\nu_{12}=\nu_{13}$	0.32			$G_{IIC}=G_{IIIC}$ (kJ/m ²)	1.0
ν_{23}	0.436			η	1.0

Table 1: Material properties for the ply and interface [1].

Figure 4: Finite element models for $[45_4/90_4/-45_4/0_4]_s$ and $[45/90/-45/0]_s$ laminates.

Figure 5: Another two in-plane meshes.

3.2 Numerical results

The load-displacement curves of the PL laminate predicted with three FE models (mesh-1, mesh-2 and mesh-3) are shown in Fig. 6. Consistent results are obtained, showing the mesh independence of the current method. All curves are linear at the early stages and slight softening occur after the force reaches 46 kN. The peak force values predicted (52.9 kN) is close to the experimental failure load, 54.3 kN.

Figure 6: Load-displacement curves of $[45_4/90_4/-45_4/0_4]_s$ laminate.

The damage growth modelled for the PL laminate with ‘mesh-1’ model is presented in Fig. 7. An initial damage occurred at $u=0.16 \text{ mm}$ given in Fig. 7 (a) shows the splitting in the middle 0° plies and limited delamination. Further loading to 90-95% failure load triggers the propagation of the matrix cracks and delamination near the cracks and also two edges in Fig. 7 (b), which shows agreement with the experimental results given in Fig. 7 (g). At the peak force value, fiber damage (red) starts propagating in the 0° plies from the hole edge in Fig. 7 (d). The deformation configuration at the peak point is given in Fig. 7 (e), showing the kinking induced by the splitting at surface plies. The out-of-plane displacement due to kinking and buckling can be further enlarged with further loading and the final deformation is given in Fig. 7 (f), where the largest displacement in the z direction (out-of-plane) reaches 0.43 mm . The modelled push-out failure patterns are verified by the experimental results in Fig. 7 (h), in which several splitting and sub-laminate buckling due to delaminations are observed.

Figure 7: Failure patterns and deformation configuration: numerical and experimental results of $[45_4/90_4/-45_4/0_4]_s$ laminate (M&D: matrix cracking and delamination; F: fiber damage).

The simulation results of the SL laminate are given in Fig. 8 and Fig. 9. The predicted peak load (45.7 kN) is close to the average failure load 47.5 kN from experiments. It is lower than the failure load of the PL laminate (54.3 kN), due to different damage events (Fig. 9). At 90% failure load (Fig. 9 (a) and Fig. 9 (e)), matrix cracks and delamination are localized around the hole edge and large splitting in 0° plies (Fig. 7 (b)) is not found. The propagation of matrix cracks is limited due to the greater constraints of adjacent plies in the sublaminates-level scaled lay-up. Therefore, the relief of stress concentration due to fiber splitting does not occur in the SL laminate. Further loading promotes the growth of subcritical damage modes (Fig. 9 (b)) but the damage zone is not extensive. The fiber damage starts propagating at the peak load value (Fig. 9 (c)), which finally results in a sudden load drop. The final deformation configuration is given in Fig. 9 (d) and obvious local bulge with a maximum out-of-plane displacement 0.8 mm at the outer surface is predicted. The failure pattern of a brittle fracture straight across the laminate agrees with the experimental observation (Fig. 9 (f)).

Figure 8: Load-displacement curve of $[45/90/-45/0]_{4s}$ laminate.

Figure 9: Failure patterns and deformation configuration: numerical and experimental results of [45/90/-45/0]_{4s} laminate

4 CONCLUSION

In this work, we present a high-fidelity predictive model of composite laminate failure under compressive loading. Matrix cracking is simulated by a discrete crack model, in which the onset is determined by the Mohr-Coulomb type criterion and shear sliding is simulated by a vertical cohesive element but with an inclined local coordinate. Fiber damage and delamination are modelled by the typical smeared crack model and cohesive zone model, respectively. The approach was applied to failure prediction of open-hole compression laminates with two types of lay-ups. Push-out failure of [45₄/90₄/-45₄/0₄]_s laminate and brittle failure of [45/90/-45/0]_{4s} laminate are predicted, which agree well with the experimental observations.

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